

Development of an Online Computer Game for the Visitors in Exhibition Halls of the Archaeological Museum – Veliko Tarnovo

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Recently, the multimedia and entertainment game products are gaining in popularity as interesting additions to museum exhibitions. Big galleries and museums all over the world are offering their visitors all sort of electronic information, combined with attractive images and texts. In some of them, are even developed 2D and 3D video games, as for instance the quest games featuring some exhibitions or puzzle games developed for the children, which can entertain them, while they are arranging jigsaw puzzles with the images of familiar culture landmarks. The idea is to attract more visitors by combining entertainment with acquiring information.

The demo presents the development of the R. M. H. V. T computer game (Hidden objects) which is to be used by the visitors of the Museum of Archeology of Veliko Tarnovo. The idea is to offer a game in which is to be sought for scattered (or lost) artifacts. The visitor looks for hidden objects that are part of the museum exhibition.

The game is developed by Unity engine, were used various scripts. The RMHV T features several maps, different ages and several items, part of the exhibition, hidden that have to be found. The scenario is done in the most intriguing and entertaining way, with lot of information, interesting facts and possibilities for upgrading. By the means of it the character – a treasure seeker, that uses a metal detector in order to complete his quest finds hidden treasures - such as gold bracelets, prehistoric, antique and mediaeval ceramic pots. In this way, the visitor is acquiring additional information about the artifact that has been virtually “found”, and at the same time becomes familiar with its functions and content.

Example scenario – REVEALED SECRET.

The gold treasure from Hotniza is one of the oldest gold treasures in the world that had been processed by a human hand. It is kept in the Regional Museum of History – Veliko Tarnovo and it is lost. Let`s find hidden items.

The game is still in a process of further development, because the complexity of the further levels derives the use of additional script codes.

